

MODEL AND TOURISM DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY BASED ON LOCAL POTENCY IN MERANGIN REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

Tourism potency and attractiveness in Merangin Regency are very diverse and spread in several districts which become tourist attractions both domestic and foreign tourists. The tourism sector in Merangin district is managed by local government, making tourism development less than optimal, it is seen with additional facilities such as home stays (hotels / inns), the mainstay products of tourist areas produced by public and access to public vehicles that can go to tourist sites. In the development of tourism, not only the government does the other parties themselves, it also contributes to infrastructure development. In developing tourism potency based on regional potential in Merangin district there are 11 alternative strategies, namely: Focusing road infrastructure to destination area, cooperation with the private sector in developing regional tourism, increasing tourism promotion in collaboration with tourism bureau in the form of Merangin tour packages, tourism promotion which is more intense, provides faster and cheaper licensing and legality for tourism bureau in Merangin Regency, repairs existing facilities and infrastructure, development of other natural tourism objects, fosters tourism-aware community development, guidance and development of Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) by region-specific, increasing Tourism Human Resources both from the government and from the private sector and the government in cooperation with SMEs increases the promotion of local specialties. The tourism sector development model in Merangin Regency is the cooperation amongst of all existing components ranging from local government, the private sector, and the community in Merangin district itself.

Keywords: Tourism, Strategy, Potency, Models and Strategies

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector is a sector that can support regional economic growth if managed properly and will reduce the dependence of region on the exploitation of natural resources. The enhancement of tourism industry output in turn leads to an increase in the living standards of those involved (Mason, 2003). Tourism development is one of the developments that need to be developed because this sector can increase the country's foreign exchange reserves, produce rapid economic growth in providing employment, increasing income, living standards and stimulating other production factors (Lickorish, 1994).

Jambi Province is a province that has a large tourism potential, some districts in Jambi Province are tourist visiting areas that are visited by numerous tourists, such as Kerinci regency, Bungo regency, Sarolangun regency and Merangin regency are areas that have great natural tourism potential.

The potential of objects and attractions in Merangin Regency which is very diverse and spread in several districts there is a tourist attraction both domestic and foreign tourists. In 2017 the number of tourists were visiting Merangin Regency consisted of 900 domestic tourists and 100 foreign tourists, by 2018 the number of foreign tourists visiting the Regency was 165 people, and more than 1,000 domestic tourists. This increase in tourist numbers is due to the promotion of both print and electronic media and social media (Dinas Kebudayaan, Pariwisata dan Olah Raga Kabupaten merangin, 2018).

The tourism sector in Merangin regency is managed by local government, so that tourism development is less than optimal, it can be seen by the lack of tourist facilities such as home stays (hotel / inn), the mainstay of tourism products produced by the community and access to public vehicles that can go to tourist sites which exists. In the development of tourism, it is not only the government that conducts it-self, but other parties also contribute to development of companion infrastructure to increase revenue from the economic sector. For this development, approaches need to be made with existing tourism organizations (government and private) and related parties which are expected to support the continued development of the area's tourism.

Based on the research of (Perdue, Long, & Allen, 1990), states that the population characteristics will have an impact on the development of tourism in an area, the same thing addressed by research conducted by (McGehee & Andereck, 2004) suggests that residents will receive a positive impact from tourism development and resist the impact negative of the development of tourism. Research conducted by (Binns & Nelt, 2002) concluded that the development of the tourism sector could reduce rates poverty, improve the economy of local people and reduce the dominance of apartheid in Africa South.

Therefore, the development of the tourism sector will have a multiplier effect on the region for Merangin Regency development of tourism sector in Merangin Regency should involve all parties, both the district government, the private sector, the community and academics to achieve good acceleration is created from various parties and the potential of the existing tourism sector can be developed which will directly have an impact on increasing the income of local communities.

In Merangin Regency, there are many natural tourism objects that have great potential, including wang bay tourism, pauh lake, masurai mountain, hesti flower garden and Merangin geopark. To all these attractions should provide great benefits, both for the community. For this reason, it is necessary to have a strategy and model in developing tourism based on the existing tourism potential. The development of the tourism sector is a good alternative to be carried out in order to increase the role of this sector in the surrounding community and the economy of Merangin Regency.

The purpose of this research is first to understand and analyse the tourism sector development strategy in Merangin District and the second is analyse the model of tourism management based on regional potency in Merangin Regency

LITERATURE REVIEW

TOURISM

According to law number 10/2009 concerning tourism are all activities related to tourism and are multidimensional and multidisciplinary in nature which emerge as a manifestation of the needs of each person and the State as well as interactions between tourists and the local community, fellow tourists, the government, regional governments and entrepreneurs. There are 4 components forming tourism, through the tourism industry, tourist destinations, marketing and tourism institutions. All efforts undertaken in the development of tourism are aimed at maximizing tourist visits or also called tourism offers.

TOURISM PLANNING

Tourism policy provides a basic philosophy for development and determines the direction of tourism development in destination for future. A destination can be said to be developing tourism if there were previously tourist activities. In the implementation of development, planning is a factor that needs to be done and considered. According to (Inskeep & Organization, 1998) there are several approaches to be considered in planning, including:

- a) Continuous Incremental, and Flexible Approach, where planning is seen as an ongoing process based on needs by monitoring existing feed backs.
- b) System Approach, whereby tourism seen as a system relationship and needs to be planned as with system analysis techniques
- c) Comprehensive Approach, related to the system approach above, where all aspects of tourism development including institutional elements and the environment and socio-economic implications as a holistic approach
- d) Integrated Approach related to the overall system approach where tourism is planned and developed as a system and overall where tourism is planned and developed as an integrated system in all plans and total forms of development in the area.
- e) Environmental and sustainable development approach, tourism is planned, developed, and managed in a way where natural and cultural resources do not experience a decline in quality and are expected to remain sustainable so an analysis of environmental carrying capacity needs to be applied to this approach.
- f) Community Approach, the approach emphasizes the importance of maximizing the involvement of local communities in the planning and decision making process of tourism, to be able to increase the desires and possibilities, it is necessary to maximize community participation in the development and management carried out in tourism and its social economic benefits.
- g) Implementable Approach, tourism development policies, plans, and recommendations are formulated to be realistic and applicable, with the techniques used are implementation techniques including development, action programs or strategies, especially in identifying and adopting.
- h) Application of systematic planning approach, this approach is applied in tourism planning based on the logic of the activity. The aims to increase visitor satisfaction, diversify the tourism market, increase the contribution of tourism to the local economy, and develop the tourism potential of an area. While objectives aim to direct actions that will help achieve development goals.

The Third World tourism industry will be threatened by many of the problems that have plagued other outward-oriented development strategies in the South during the postwar era, alternative tourism development strategies must be designed either alone or together with the main tourism, so that tourism development can develop simultaneously and can reduce the negative impacts and increase the positive impact of the development of tourism (Brohman, 1996).

According Jovanovic (2008), Geographic Information Systems (GIS) , in the tourism industry used to provide: (a) A digital map base for printed maps; (b) Digital files for internet mapping; (c) Digital files for mobile mapping; (d) Attractions map and (e) Website with interactive mapping. GIS technology offers great opportunities for the development of modern tourism application using maps.

TOURISM SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT MODEL

According to World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) cited in Dewi (2011), sustainable development is development that meets the necessary of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. To carry out sustainable development, development must increase efficiency economically, protect and restore the ecological system and improve the welfare of humanity.

Whereas the tourism sustainable development is sustainable development achieved through tourism. Sustainable development is a long-term economic development, which balances economic benefits with environmental and social costs. Sustainable tourism development aims to realize sustainable tourism growth. Sustainable tourism development is achieved by balancing three main elements in sustainable tourism development which are environmental, economic and social which show general principles in sustainable tourism, through:

1. Balancing the use of environment with the economic benefits of tourism.
2. Balancing the use of environmental resources with changes in social and community values caused by the reduction of environmental resources,
3. Balancing the economic growth and the impact of economic growth on social and economic values.

The term sustainable tourism is an industry that strives to make the least impact on the environment and local culture, while helping to bring in income, create jobs, and conserve ecosystems. This responsibility encompasses a sensitive environment and culture. The WTP on its website explains that sustainable tourism as tourism which directs the management of all sources is carried out in such a way that needs, economic, social and beauty can be met while maintaining cultural integrity, essential ecological processes, biodiversity and life support systems in the environment concerned (Ernawati, 2010). According to (Lee & Kim, 2016), the results of the analysis state that community attachment and community involvement are the main factors that have an impact on sustainable tourism development.

METHODOLOGY

TYPE AND DATA SOURCE

This research utilising primary and secondary data. Primary data regarding information about the potentials of attractions. The data was obtained directly from observations and interviews with related agencies.

Secondary data regarding the development of these attractions. The data was obtained from published by statistics bureau, the compilation of data from Merangin Regency Tourism and Sports Youth Office and other relevant publications and sources.

COLLECTING DATA METHOD

Primary data collected directly to the object of research by the method:

1. Observation Method
Observe the existing tourist objects regarding infrastructure and infrastructure that is in the vicinity of the tourist area.
2. Questionnaire Method
There are 5 research sampel, Tourism institution, travel agent, academia, public works office and regional office for planning and development.
3. Interview Method
Interviews were conducted concurrently with respondents to better understand the conditions of tourism in the Merangin Regency

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Data analysis method used in this research are descriptive-qualitative. Qualitative descriptive method is used by describing writing based on interpretation based on the current situation. To formulate a strategy for developing tourism sector in Merangin regency, data analysis was carried out using a SWOT analysis. According to David (2006), there were three stages in the formulation of the strategy, through: The First Stage is the input stage, such as External Factor Evaluation Matrix (EFE) matrix is a tool used to examine the company's external environment and to identify opportunities and threats that exist, Compotitive Profile Matriks (CPM) is tool that compares companies and their competitors and reveals their relative strengths and

weaknesses, and the Internal Factor Evaluation Matrix (IFE) is a tool used to evaluate a company's internal environment and reveal its strengths and weaknesses ; 2) matching stages, such as Strength-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threat Matrix (SWOT), and the Strategies Position and Action Evaluation Matrix (SPACE) is one of the matrices used by a company to determine strategy is most appropriate to be applied, Boston Consulting Group Matrix (BCG) is an analytical tool used to assist companies in considering growth opportunities with long-term strategic planning and assist in the allocation of appropriate resource locations, Internal-External Matrix (IE) include the company's internal strengths and external influences faced by the company to obtain business strategies, and grand strategy matrix; and 3) the decision stage, such as the quantitative strategy planning matrix (QSPM) is a matrix that constructs alternative strategies, based on the key internal and external success factors identified earlier.

According to (Rangkuti, 2014), the steps taken in the formulation of the strategy are as follows:

1. Data collection stage

This stage is basically not just data collection, but also a classification and pre-analysis activity. At this stage the data can be divided into two namely internal and external data. The model used at this stage is the analysis of internal and external factors by compiling in the Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS) table.

2. Analysis Phase

After all data affecting the development of coffee commodities in Jambi Province are collected, proceed to the analysis stage through a strategy formulation model with a SWOT matrix.

3. Phase Matching Strategy for tourism development in Merangin Regency

From the SWOT matrix we will get alternative strategies as shown in the following figure :

Table 1. Matriks SWOT

IFA/EFA	STRENGTHS (S)	WEAKNES (W)
OPPORTUNITIES (O)	SO Strategy	WO Strategy
	Creating a strategy use force to utilize opportunity if it's on quadrant I	Creating a strategy minimize weaknesses to utilize opportunity. Use if is in quadrant III
TREATHS (T)	ST Strategy	WT Strategy
	Creating a strategy use force to overcome threats. Used if located at quadrant II	Creating a strategy minimize weaknesses and avoid threats. Used if located at quadrant IV

4. Development Strategy Decision Making Stage

After matching the internal and external factors, a decision is made to determine the main strategy through the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) analysis tool. QSPM uses input from stage 1 (IFE dan EFE matrix) and matching results from stage 2 (SWOT). After the scores from IFE and EFE is revealed, than those scores will be calculated with the questionnaire score from SWOT which shows the strategic alternative. The result of the calculation will be captured in Total Attractiveness Score (TAS). The highest score of TAS presents the strategic priority that should be done. To develop an integrated model of tourism development. As for the stages as follows: (1). Qualitative Descriptive Analysis (stage 1), (2) Focus Group Discussion (FGD), stages 2 and (3) Conclusions Model of tourism development in Merangin Regency in Jambi Province (Phase 3).

This research discusses only on tourism strategy and development in Merangin regency based on its tourism potential. Further, this research will discuss about tourism promotion based on digital promotion.

RESULT

TOURISM SECTOR DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN MERANGIN REGENCY

Identification of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

Identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats are important factors in conducting a SWOT analysis. For the analysis of the internal environment, the identification made is a strength factor and a weakness factor, while for an external environmental analysis the factors identified are the opportunity factor and the threat factor. After these factors are identified, it will produce various alternative strategies, then the best strategy is chosen.

1. Strength

The strengths possessed by Merangin tourism are:

- a. A beautiful tourist attraction, original and has special characteristics
- b. Fresh Air
- c. Profound Government Support
- d. Good Security Conditions

2. Weakness

Weaknesses in tourism development in Merangin district are:

- a. Tourism promotion is still low
- b. Inadequate facilities and supporting infrastructure for tourism
- c. The absence of public transportation to reach tourist attractions
- d. Lack of HR in Tourism
- e. The government budget is still limited to the tourism sector

3. Opportunities

- a. There are still numerous natural tourism objects that have not yet been developed
- b. The existence of tour and travel agents
- c. There are SMEs that provide local specialties

4. Threats

- a. Lack of community support for tourism facilities
- b. Poorest Road Infrastructure
- c. The existence of Travel Destinations in Other Regencies

Alternative Formulation of Tourism Development Strategy in Merangin Regency

After identifying and analyzing the internal and external environmental conditions of tourism development based on regional potency in Merangin regency, the next step is the formulation of strategies to be carried out. The strategy formulation is carried out through three stages, namely the input stage which includes the IFE matrix and EFE matrix, the matching stage which includes the IE matrix and the SWOT matrix, and the decision-making stage using the QSPM matrix.

1. Matriks IFE

The IFE matrix is used to find out how big the role of internal factors is in the development of regional potential based tourism in Merangin District.

Table 2. IFE Matrix Model and Tourism-Based Development Strategy Regional Potential in Merangin Regency

Factor Strategis Internal	Point	Rate	Score
Strength			
1. Attractions beautiful, original and has a characteristic	0,108	3,750	0,404
2. Cool air	0,134	3,000	0,401
3. Large Government Support	0,083	3,750	0,365
4. Good security conditions	0,097	3,500	0,345
Weakness			
1. Tourism promotion is still low	0,128	2,000	0,257
2. Inadequate facilities and supporting infrastructure for tourism	0,097	1,750	0,170
3. The absence of public transportation to reach tourist attractions	0,095	2,000	0,191
4. Lack of human resources in the Field of Tourism	0,161	1,750	0,283
5. The government budget is still limited to the tourism sector	0,095	1,500	0,143
Total	1		2,522

Source: Processed from Questioners, 2019

Based on IFE table above, it is known that the strength factor that has the highest score is a beautiful, original tourist attraction and has a unique characteristic with a score of 0,404. The second highest score is owned by the cool air with a score of 0,401, this is not surprising because natural tourism in the Merangin Regency is still original and beautiful as well as tourist destinations close to Mount Masurai in the Merangin District. Government support obtained a score of 0,365 which is in the third position of strength owned by the Merangin district. The Merangin district government provides strong support for the development of the tourism sector in this area which can be seen from the regional vision and mission.

The main weakness in development of tourism in the Merangin regency is the limited government budget with a score of 0,143. With a limited budget command the tourism sector will require a long time in the provision of tourism facilities, facilities and infrastructure, the provision of tourism facilities, facilities and infrastructure will have an impact on tourism development more quickly, therefore the need for investment from the private sector in tourism management areas in Merangin Regency. The second weakness in tourism development in Merangin Regency is the inadequate tourism supporting facilities and infrastructure with a score of 0,170, the existing tourism facilities and infrastructure will be very closely related to the number of tourist visits to the region.

Overall, the total weighted score of strengths and weaknesses in IFE matrix is 2,522. Thus, the internal condition of regional potential based tourism development in Merangin district is above the average value of 2,50. Based on the total weighted values, it can be concluded that the development of tourism in the Merangin district is in a strong position in utilizing the strengths it has and is capable enough to overcome weaknesses.

2. Matriks EFE

The EFE matrix is used to determine the effect of external factors faced in tourism development in Merangin District. seen in Table 4.2.

Table. 3. EFE Matrix Model and Tourism Development Strategy Based On Regional Potency in Merangin Regency

Factor Strategy External	Weight	Rating	weight score
Opportunity			
1. There are still many natural tourism objects that have not yet been developed	0,171	4	0,683
2. The existence of tour and travel agents	0,171	2,25	0,384
3. The existence of micro and small businesses that provide local specialties	0,188	2,75	0,516
Threat			
1. Lack of community support for tourism facilities	0,158	2,5	0,396
2. Road infrastructure that is not good yet	0,092	2,5	0,229
3. The existence of tourist destinations in other districts	0,221	2,25	0,497

Source: Processed from Questioners, 2019

Based on EFE matrix table, the main opportunity is there are still numerous non-developed tourism objects with the highest score of 0,683. This score shows that tourism development in Merangin district is still wide open with many natural tourism desires that have not yet been developed, even have not been touched by the local government at all. A score of 0,516 is owned by the presence of SMEs that provide local specialties.

The main threat factor that must be faced in the development of tourism in the Merangin district is the unfavorable road infrastructure with a score of 0,229, the main road infrastructure leading to the tourist destination is still not good, this is seen by the still many rocky and perforated roads coupled with terrain quite a terrible road. Another threat faced in the development of tourism in Merangin district is the lack of community support for tourism facilities. Overall, the total weighted score from three opportunities and three threats in the EFE matrix is 2,705 or above the average value of 2,50. Based on the total weighted values, it can be concluded that the development of regional-based tourism potential in Merangi Regency is able to respond to the external environment by utilizing the opportunities they have to face threats.

3. IE Matrix

IE matrix is arranged based on the analysis of internal and external factors combined from the IFE matrix and the EFE matrix. IE matrix can be seen in Figure 4.1 below:

Figure 1. IE Matrix Tourism Development in Merangin Regency Jambi Province

The results of internal factor analysis by using the IFE matrix obtained a weighted total score of 2,545. While the results of the analysis of external factors using the EFE matrix obtained a weighted total score of 2,705. Based on the total weighted score from the IFE and EFE matrix, the development of regional potential based tourism in Merangin Regency is in cell V in the IE matrix. The strategy that can be taken at the position of the cell is the Hold and Maintain Strategy.

4. SWOT Matrix

The SWOT matrix is compiled based on the results of the identification and analysis of internal and external factors, including strengths and weaknesses that are owned as well as opportunities and threats that must be faced. The integration of internal and external factors in the SWOT matrix will result in several alternative strategies that can be used in the development of regional-based tourism potential in the Merangin regency. The SWOT matrix can produce four sets of possible alternative strategies namely S-O strategy, S-T strategy, W-O strategy and W-T strategy. The strategies generated from the SWOT matrix can be seen below.

Table 4. SWOT Matrix Tourism Development Based On Local Potency in Merangin Regency

Internal Factors External Factors	Strength (S) 1. A beautiful, original and distinctive attraction 2. Cool air 3. Large Government Support 4. Good security condition	Weakness (W) 1. Tourism promotion is still low 2. Inadequate tourism supporting facilities and infrastructure 3. The absence of public transportation to reach tourist attractions 4. Lack of human resources in the field of tourism 5. The government budget is still limited to the tourism sector
	Opportunity 1. There are still natural tourism objects that have not yet been developed 2. The existence of tour and travel agents 3. The existence of SMEs that provide local specialties	S – O Strategy 1. Development of other natural attractions (S1 and O1) 2. The government works in cooperation with SMEs to increase the promotion of regional specialties (S3 and O3) 3. Provide faster and cheaper licensing and legality for tourism bureaus in Merangin District (S3, S4 and W2)
Threat 1. The lack of community support in tourism area 2. Low quality of road infrastructure 3. There are another tourism areas in other regions	S – T Strategy 1. Developing tourism-aware communities (S3 and T1) 2. Focusing road infrastructure to tourist destination areas (S3, T1 and T2)	W – T Strategy 1. Cooperation with the private sector in the development of regional tourism (W 2 and W5, T2) 2. More intensive tourism promotion (W1 and T3)

Source: Processed from Questioners, 2019

5. QSPM Matrix

The final stage of the strategy formulation analysis is the decision making stage, through the selection of best strategy according to priority using the QSPM matrix. After obtaining several alternative strategies for developing regional-based tourism potential in Merangin District, the selection of alternative strategies is prioritized to be implemented using the QSPM matrix. The strategy chosen to be implemented is based on the results of the QSPM analysis calculations shown in the table below.

Table 5. QSPM Matrix Alternative for Tourism Sector Development Strategy Based on Regional Potential in Merangin Regency

Strategy	Relationship	TAS Total Attractiveness Score	Rank
1. Development of other natural attractions	(S1 and O1)	4,315	7
2. The government cooperates with SMEs to increase the promotion of regional specialties	(S3 and O3)	3,829	11
3. Provide faster and cheaper licensing and legality for tourism bureaus in Merangin Regency	(S3, S4 and W2)	4,386	5
4. Increasing tourism promotion in collaboration with travel agencies in the form of Merangin tour packages	(S1 and O2)	4,663	3
5. Repair of existing facilities and infrastructure	(S2, O1 and O2)	4,384	6
6. Increasing Tourism Human Resources both from the government apparatus and from the private sector	(S4 and S2)	3,886	10
7. Coaching and developing SMEs by - by special regions	(S2 and O3)	3,912	9
8. Grow and develop tourism-aware society	(S3 and T1)	4,160	8
9. Focusing road infrastructure on tourist destination areas	(S3, T1 and T2)	4,956	1
10. Cooperation with the private sector in developing regional tourism	(W 2 and W5, T2)	4,890	2
11. More intensive tourism promotion	(W1 and T3)	4,659	4

Source: Processed from Questioners, 2019

Based on the QSPM matrix above, alternative priority strategies that can be carried out by the Merangin district government in developing the tourism sector based on regional potential are:

1. On focusing of road infrastructure to tourist destination areas with a TAS value of 4.956. This strategy is a priority strategy in the development of the tourism sector because with a good road infrastructure, tourists will become more interested in visiting these attractions.
2. Cooperation with the private sector in development of regional tourism with a TAS value of 4,890. It means that there is a need for financial assistance from the private sector both from the domestic private sector or through foreign investment.
3. Increased tourism promotion in collaboration with travel agencies in the form of Merangin tour packages with a TAS value of 4.663. Offering Merangin tour packages through travel agents will be more attractive for tourists
4. More vigorous tourism promotion is a strategy to develop the fourth tourism sector with a TAS value of 4.659. With the promotion of tourism that is more intense the number of tourists who come to be more and the development of the tourism sector in the Merangin district can run faster.

5. Providing faster and cheaper licensing and legality for tourism agency in Merangin regency is the 5th strategy with a TAS value of 4.386, this will have an impact on the emergence of new tourism bureaus and improve performance at bureaus tourism in attracting tourist visits and will have an impact on the development of the tourism sector in Merangin regency.
6. The 6th strategy in developing the tourism sector is the improvement of existing facilities and infrastructure, with the improvement of tourist facilities and infrastructure, the tourists feel comfortable, happy and want to return to visit the tourist destination
7. Development of other natural attractions with a TAS value of 4,315. Merangin Regency still has tourism objects that have not yet been developed that have the same potential as other tourism objects that already exist today. If the local government develops tourism objects with the necessary facilities and infrastructure, then the opportunity to attract greater tourist arrivals to come to the Merangin district is more open.
8. Developing tourism-aware society is the 8th strategy with a TAS value of 4.160. Currently the community tourism awareness movement in Merangin Regency is one of the efforts made by the local government through the rural tourism community
9. The 9th tourism sector development strategy is the fostering and development of SMEs by regional specialists with a TAS value of 3,912. Development of SMEs by local specialties can be carried out with training and product marketing development, this needs to be done because local specialties in Merangin district are still very narrow in their marketing reach and are still difficult to find.
10. Improving of Tourism HR both from the government apparatus and from the private sector with a TAS value of 3,886. This increase in HR will have an impact on the development of the tourism sector by making tourism management safer, more comfortable and sustainable.
11. The final strategy in the development of the tourism sector in Merangin Regency is that the Government in cooperation with SMEs promotes the promotion of local specialties, making regional souvenirs one of the icons sought by tourists.

REGIONAL POTENCY BASED TOURISM SECTOR DEVELOPMENT MODEL IN MERANGIN REGENCY

The development of the tourism sector must involve all parties, ranging from the central government, local governments, the private sector and the community around the tourist attraction. The development of the tourism sector will have an impact on increasing local revenue, empowering the surrounding community and increasing people's income from the existence of these attractions.

Figure 2. Model Tourism Development Based on Local Potency in Merangin Regency

There are 3 components involved in development of tourism sector in Merangin regency, through local government, private sector and community. The local government provides the main road infrastructure to attractions with good conditions, as well as the roads are around the tourist attraction, in addition to providing road infrastructure, the local government can also provide facilities and infrastructure for tourist facilities around the tourist attraction. In addition to the local government, the private sector can also participate in the development of tourism in the Merangin regency through travel bureaus by providing tour packages, and investing in tourism in the provision of tourism facilities and infrastructure.

In addition to the local government and the private sector, the community is also an important part in the development of tourism in the Merangin district. Tourism-aware community movement is one form of community movement to participate in the tourism sector by maintaining facilities and infrastructure, helping tourists visiting tourist objects, making community homes as home stays and making communities to form SMEs based on results. regional agriculture.

In many cases, alternative tourism strategies ought to be designed, either by themselves or in concert with mainstream tourism, to provide more appropriate forms of development that reduce the negative impacts and increase the positive effects of tourism. These include a stress on small-scale, locally owned developments that increase local multiplier and spread effects, greater community participation in tourism planning, and more attention for the culture and environmental sustainability of tourism projects (Brohman, 1996).

With this tourism sector development model, it can contribute to involve the sectors in the area in tourism development and novelty in this research is a new tourism development model.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. In developing tourism potency based on regional potential in Merangin regency there are 11 alternative strategies, namely: Focusing road infrastructure to the destination area, cooperation with the private sector in developing regional tourism, increasing tourism promotion in collaboration with tourism bureaus in the form of Merangin tour packages, promotion of tourism that is more intense, provides licensing and legality faster and cheaper for tourism bureaus in Merangin District, improvement of existing facilities and infrastructure, development of other natural tourism objects, fostering tourism-aware communities, fostering and developing SMEs by - by local specialties, increasing Tourism Human Resources both from the government apparatus and from the private sector and the government in collaboration with SMEs increases the promotion of regional specialties.
2. The tourism sector development model in Merangin regency is the cooperation amongst of all existing components starting from the local government, the private sector and the community in Merangin district itself.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection, analysis, writing and revising the manuscript.

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